

Teaching speaking in *Kampung Inggris*: the tutors' challenges and solutions

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Aug 7, 2023

Revised Dec 4, 2023

Accepted Dec 15, 2023

Keywords:

Challenges

Kampung Inggris

Solutions

Teaching speaking

Tutors

ABSTRACT

Teaching English speaking has become a centre of attention among scholars and teaching English to speakers of other languages (TESOL) practitioners for a few decades. However, the issue of teaching English speaking in *Kampung Inggris*/English Village remains under-researched, notably viewed from the tutors' challenges and solutions in the Indonesian English as a foreign language (EFL) milieu. This study addressed this gap. Two English tutors from *Kampung Inggris*/English Village got involved as the participants. The data were collected through semi-structured interviews and analyzed with thematic analysis. The findings reported that there were five challenges encountered by tutors when teaching English speaking, namely tutors' inability of exploring English language teaching materials, tutors' insufficient English vocabulary, tutors' ineffective time management during language teaching practices, demotivated tutees to learn English, and perceived teaching anxiety. In addition, the tutors stipulated four solutions to cope with such challenges, namely building a good rapport between tutor and tutees, tutors' self-motivation to English vocabulary enrichment, selecting appropriate and providing updated English language teaching materials, and motivating English language tutees. Therefore, teaching English speaking should not only rely on immersing students in fluency-based activities but also manage tutees' psychological factors to attain more effective teaching English speaking objectives.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Achieving language proficiency in a foreign language-speaking class is not an easy task. One of the most common problems among learners of foreign languages is their considerably lower speaking performance [1]. Thus, plenty of learners have taken English courses to facilitate their learning of English speaking [2], [3]. Since English language learning activities in a formal education (e.g. schools) have not provided sufficient exposures for students to learn English optimally, non-formal educational institutions (e.g. English courses) are perceived to be able to help them maximize such foreign language exposures [4]. Hence, learning English in a non-formal educational institution remains crucial in the last few decades.

In Indonesia, there are several well-known English language learning courses. One of them is *Kampung Inggris*/English Village. It is located in Pare, Kediri, East Java. *Kampung Inggris* creates an environment where learners have options to immerse in English within a program in a non-formal setting.

Kampung Inggris is a suitable place for non-formal education because it provides a learning opportunity for students who need more learning activities [5]. In addition, the delivered teaching materials are relatively pleasant (e.g., games-based English language learning practices). Such materials contain (e.g., ABCD 5 base, guessing pictures, and alphabet yells) [6]. The boundary between tutors and tutees is less visible to let both parties possess a well-made relationship [7]. Also, the supportive environment in learning English is very influential in practising all material. For example, there is an English area, a kind of dorm, where students are required to be silent in any language other than English.

In June 2023, one of the researchers joined a speaking class at one of the English courses in *Kampung Inggris*. One of the reasons that underlies her to participate in such a course was to improve her English-speaking skills. At the beginning of the class, in pre-activities, the tutors arranged the conversational session. It was a kind of dialogue session between tutors and tutees by asking about their life experiences or anything related to the topics to be discussed. The students were instructed to use the English language when answering the questions as much as they can or they could mix it into Indonesia. Usually, the tutees were divided into several groups and they were requested to share a story of what they had experienced (e.g. an unforgettable moment). By doing this, they can easily understand and learn the English language and also practice it.

In addition, there were games during the activities. It motivated the tutees to learn English enthusiastically. Those games could help a lot in enhancing English vocabulary. The tutors and tutees merely played games together (e.g. guess something). Both tutors and tutees positioned themselves equally and learn English collaboratively in the classroom. In other words, the tutors acted as the tutees' friends. Moreover, there was a reward if the tutees won the game. They got a snack and got smeared with baby powder on the face as punishment.

Besides, there were certainly some inhibitions encountered by the tutors. At the beginning of the class, the researcher saw the tutor was less prepared for the teaching materials. He seemed to be confused and looked nervous. In addition, some tutees came from different backgrounds (e.g. students, undergraduates, postgraduates, and jobseekers, age (e.g. range from 17 to 25 and culture (e.g. Sundanese, Javanese). As a result, it was difficult for him to organize the classroom. As an example, he was not able to answer the question posed by one of the tutees. Even though the question was about common vocabulary in a daily life, he could not discover the equivalence of such a word in English. Understanding this investigative phenomenon enables the tutors to keep developing their content knowledge before teaching.

Even though plenty of studies have emphasized teaching speaking in *Kampung Inggris* in terms of the implementation of oral corrective feedback in English as a foreign language (EFL) classroom [8], the implementation of scaffolding strategies at speaking English course in *Kampung Inggris* [9], teachers' teaching speaking strategies at EFL course in *Kampung Inggris* [10], and students' perception on English camp in *Kampung Inggris* Pare on improving their speaking skills [11], a few of them have scrutinized the English tutor's challenges and solutions during teaching English speaking in *Kampung Inggris*. For this reason, this study attempted to scrutinize the English tutors' challenges and solutions during teaching English speaking in *Kampung Inggris*.

2. METHODS

The current study was carried out in one of the English courses in *Kampung Inggris*, Pare, Kediri, East Java, Indonesia. This selection was based on the locus of investigation where the investigative phenomena took place there, namely faced teaching challenges and offered possible solutions showcased by some English tutors during teaching speaking. Two male English tutors voluntarily took part as the investigative participants. They majored English education and held the *sarjana pendidikan* (B.A. in English education) degree. They had 550 tests of English as a foreign (TOEFL) institutional testing program (ITP) score. Informed by the TOEFL ITP score descriptors and the common European framework of reference for languages (CEFR) levels, 550 points (pts) is categorised into independent user-vantage level with B2 for the CEFR level. They graduated from the English Education Department of a State University in East Java. They have taught English speaking in *Kampung Inggris* for two to five years. They have taught English for communicative purposes (e.g., English-speaking class). A consideration of recruiting only two tutors as the participants since in the English-speaking class only consisted two tutors. Another consideration was they performed their roles as professional English tutors. The participants had friendly, creative and adaptive characteristics. Specifically, they were recruited because they encountered several challenges while teaching English speaking. Also, they sought for solutions to overcome the challenges of their English language teaching practices. More importantly, they showed a willingness to participate in this study.

The data were collected through semi-structured interviews. The interviews enabled the interviewers to gain a comprehensive description of the investigated issue. The interview questions encompassed several

topics, such as challenges and potential solutions during teaching English speaking in *Kampung Inggris* adapted from the notion of teaching English problems in the EFL contexts [12].

Once the data were collected, they were analyzed with thematic analysis (hereafter, TA) [13]. In practice, the data analysis underwent six phases, namely i) familiarizing with the data, ii) generating initial codes, iii) searching for themes, iv) reviewing themes, v) defining and naming themes, and vi) producing the report [13]. By applying this data analysis technique, the data can be explored effectively to reach a comprehensive and multidimensional comprehension of research purposes [14].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Tutors' challenges in teaching English speaking in *Kampung Inggris*

3.1.1. Tutors' inability of exploring English language teaching materials

The first challenge faced by tutors when teaching English speaking in *Kampung Inggris* is the inability of exploring English language teaching materials. This incapability was caused by the difficult topics of teaching materials served in English-speaking classes (Speak UP 3 class). In particular, there was a significant shift from the easier to harder levels of teaching materials. As an example, tutor # 1 argued that the focus of teaching English speaking became challenging due to its distinctive learning levels, scope, and contents, such as more advanced teaching materials, broader discussed learning topics, and various terms wrapped in English vocabulary.

Excerpt 1: "We have to simplify difficult topics and that is quite challenging for me. It happened when I was teaching in Speak Up 3 class. The material was different from level 2 or level 1. Here, the focus is more on speaking practices and the materials were a bit more advanced. So, we have to broaden materials or topics. For example, we discussed social or economic issues. It's a bit heavy. So, it required more advanced vocabulary too so the speaking materials were more challenging (Interview transcript of the tutor # 1, June 7th, 2023)."

Further, he exemplified that social and economic issues were challenging teaching materials for English-speaking activities. Even, he claimed that these issues were heavier than the previous levels of English-speaking activities (level 1 and 2) ("for example, we discussed social or economic issues. It's a bit heavy") since comprehending and communicating these teaching materials require more advanced English vocabulary, wider insights, and updating information. Given these facts, enriching English vocabulary, familiarizing them with social issues, and exposing them to the most current information remain vital for assisting them to teach their students. Ideally, teachers should be able to develop their teaching materials to merit their students' needs [15]. This can be realized if teachers have adequate knowledge and comprehension of how language teaching materials are developed [16].

3.1.2. Tutors' ineffective time management during language teaching practices

The second challenge confronted by tutees is ineffective time management during language teaching practices. In this case, one of the tutors (tutor # 1) required more time to provide corrective feedback (hereafter, CF) to his students to their speaking performances. Besides, he acknowledged that he even spent more than 90 minutes (one lesson hour) helping tutees understand, diagnose and revise the mistakes in their speaking performances ("i want one tuteescan master his mistakes, he has to fix his mistakes, so I have to waste the time even I can usually spend more than 90 minutes (one lesson hour) well") as illustrated in the excerpt 3.

Excerpt 3: "It needs time because, in one corrective feedback, I want details, I want one tuteescan master his mistakes, he has to fix his mistakes, so I have to waste time even though I can usually spend more than 90 minutes (one lesson hour) well. Usually, I need two days for corrective feedback; I'm difficult to manage the time because I am always detailed, so sometimes I need a lot of time (Interview transcript of the tutor # 1, June 7th, 2023)."

Also, he added that he spent approximately two days giving CF to his tutees' tasks of English-speaking practices (e.g. video-mediated English-speaking tasks) because he commonly provided detailed information in his CF. This activity required him to have effective time management so that the entire teaching practices (planning, practising, and evaluating) can be successfully tackled. Nevertheless, he realized that he was not always able to manage his time effectively during teaching practices [17]. This circumstance made him more reflective of the allotted time for teaching practices. To sum up, effective time management becomes a predominant solution for tutors to effectively teach but also evaluate the tutees' English speaking competencies and performances [18].

3.1.3. Tutors' insufficient English vocabulary

Tutors' insufficient English vocabulary has also become a salient challenge when they were teaching English speaking. To illustrate, tutor # 2 had a teaching challenge when one of his tutees posed a question about the meaning of 'kelilipan' [handicapped]. On the one hand, he assumed that this word was not problematic since it commonly appeared in daily communication. On the other hand, it became challenging due to he was unable to answer it idiomatically.

Excerpt 4: "The obstacle for me is that in class, I like to be asked about strange vocabulary or words that we always use in daily life or maybe the sentences they often find in movies or songs, and when they look for it in the dictionary, there is no such thing, for example, someone asks 'if it's kelilipan in English, what is it bro?' then I answered. I got something in my eyes (Interview transcript of tutor # 2, June 9th, 2023)."

As described above, he thought that such a tuteegained the question inspired by a movie or a song enjoyed by the tutee. However, he did not find the meaning of such a word (kelilipan) in the dictionary. As a result, he asked his tutor ("Someone asks 'if it's kelilipan in English, what is it, bro?"). To answer the question, tutor # 2 spontaneously improvised to raise the clause 'I got something in my eyes. Even though this clause did not provide the contextual answer, it functioned as an alternative answer. By doing so, he did not only save his face in front of his tutees as an English tutor but also facilitated his tutees to enrich their English vocabulary [19].

3.1.4. Demotivated tutees to learn English

Viewed from the internal challenges of teaching English speaking, tutors were demotivated to learn. In particular, both tutor # 1 and # 2 faced psychological barriers when they played their roles as tutors of English speaking. As an example, tutor # 1 perceived anxiety, shyness, and afraid of making mistakes while teaching ("Anxiety, shyness or afraid of being mistaken by students"). These uncomfortable situations lead to learning demotivation. They felt that they did not deserve to be English tutors due to various self-limitations. Unfortunately, he did not explicitly explain why and how these psychological problems occurred.

Excerpt 5: "Anxiety, shyness, or afraid of being mistaken by students, huh? Yes, it's a challenge; most teachers will face this challenge (Interview transcript of the tutor # 1, June 7th, 2023). Mmm, a challenge, maybe the first one was to make the tutees comfortable in the first meeting because there are a number of what ... their names ... feel 'oh, I'm inferior, I'm embarrassed, I just want to move, how come it's hard. The problem is in encouraging them to stay in class to join meetings or study (Interview transcript of tutor # 2, June 7th, 2023)."

Referring to the aforementioned excerpt, tutor # 2 also indicated a similar challenge, namely internal psychological issues. As a matter of fact, he argued that he was inferior while acting as an English tutor. This led him to have less self-confidence and be demotivated to teach. Besides, he felt embarrassed of his audience (tutees) when initially performing in front of the class. These psychological issues not only affect the tutors to teach but also to learn as a bridge to reach professional development. Thus, peer support among tutors remains crucial.

3.1.5. Perceived teaching anxiety

Perceived teaching anxiety is another inevitable challenge experienced by tutors. Both tutor # 1 and # 2 underwent this situation when they were teaching English speaking in front of tutees. For example, tutor # 1 uttered that he felt reluctant while teaching tutees. The reluctance originated from the tutees' ages (e.g. 17, 20, 25 years old) and occupations (e.g. lecturers, sailors, and post-graduate students). More specifically, he explicated that the ages of his tutees ranged from 17 to 25 years old. Meanwhile, the tutors' ages were younger than theirs, such as Tutor # 1 (20) and Tutor # 2 (22). Then, the tutees' occupations also indirectly affected the tutors-tutees' reports. As an illustration, tutors should be able to employ appropriate communication and politeness strategies when interacting with them since tutees may be more experienced, knowledgeable, and skilful. As a result, both tutors perceived that they were inferior in front of their tutees.

Excerpt 6: "Hmm ... when it comes to ages, it's usually mixed up. In class, some are 17, 20 years, 25 years old. Some are already undergraduates or working or some are lecturers, sailors, some have graduated and some are still in high school mix in terms of age or background education. The challenge is I feel inferior because in class there are lecturers, so in the class sometimes it becomes "Oh how come ... there are lecturers here (Interview transcript of the tutor # 1, June 7th, 2023)."

Excerpt 7: “Well, there is a challenge in this, for example, there used to be a lecturer from a university where he was majoring in nutrition, nutrition. Well, in-class days one to three, his gaze is very intimidating to me, and I get nervous when teaching (Interview transcript of the tutor # 1, June 9th, 2023).”

Likewise, tutors did not only perceive mediocrity but also anxiety while teaching their tutees. This anxiety emerged from their unconfidence and nervousness as well. To illustrate, tutor # 2 had never felt intimidated when he was teaching a lecturer majoring in the nutrition department. He described that the perceived intimidation came from the tutee's gaze when he was learning English speaking. Unfortunately, he did not provide further information on why it took place. Generally speaking, perceived teaching anxiety can be identified from internal (e.g. nervousness, reluctance, and doubt) and external factors (e.g. age discrepancy, educational background, and professions).

3.2. Potential solutions to overcome the challenges

3.2.1. Building a good rapport between the tutor and tutees

The first solution revealed by tutors is building a good rapport with tutors and tutees. This solution facilitated how tutors interacted with tutees to tackle the tutors' incapability of exploring English language teaching materials, demotivated tutors to learn English, and perceived teaching anxiety. For instance, tutor # 1 motivated his tutees to feel comfortable, close, and enjoyable learning activities. He mentioned that this motivation was aimed at raising the chemistry of tutors and tutees. Besides, the tutor-tutees rapport was established through language learning games to reduce the tutees' reluctance and tutors' teaching anxiety as in excerpt 8.

Excerpt 8: “I motivate my students, of them is by presenting learning activities that are enjoyable so ... what makes them comfortable and close to me, I go back to building chemistry, no boundaries, so I'm not ashamed to ask ... or it can be with games like that (Interview transcript of the tutor # 1, June 7th, 2020).”

Excerpt 9: “I created an atmosphere and interesting learning activities for them, like games. It also helps to build closeness between me and the tutees. Well, when they start laughing, they start to be cool and not awkward, by building chemistry, and then they start practising speaking up. For example, learning how to get longer conversations with the methods they finally feel good, God willing, the learning process can enter (Interview transcript of the tutor # 2, June 7th, 2023).”

In a similar vein, tutor # 2 expressed relatively similar arguments to tutor # 1 about the significance of establishing a good rapport among tutors and tutees. He noted that creating an interesting, enjoyable, and close learning atmosphere remains crucial for tutors to engage tutees in the entire learning activities, notably in English speaking class [18]. In addition, this effort was to activate the chemistry among tutors and tutees. For instance, tutors began their teaching activities by laughing, keeping relaxed, and performing natural acts (“Well, when they start laughing, they start to be cool and not awkward, by building chemistry, then they start practising speaking up”). Once they were comfortable with the conditioned classroom atmosphere, tutors requested them to actively speak up [20].

3.2.2. Tutors' self-motivation for English vocabulary enrichment

Tutors' self-motivation to English vocabulary enrichment is one of the solutions to overcome the challenges, such as their incapability of exploring English language teaching materials and insufficient English vocabulary. These challenges require tutors to be able to master English vocabulary. Therefore, they need high self-motivation for English vocabulary enrichment.

Excerpt 9: “For example, we often hear the word famous, so here I try to replace it with widely known or well-known. Or um ... another example like 'delay' can be replaced with 'temporize' 'procrastinate' and 'postpone'. That vocabulary I introduced to tutees in my class. Now, the next challenge is hmm ... for example, if a tutee doesn't know about vocabulary or less in the vocabulary. Moreover, the topic is quite heavy. It means we have to increase our vocabulary first, as a new tutor is taught or taught to tutees because the key to speaking is vocabulary (Interview transcript of the tutor # 1, June 7th, 2023).”

From excerpt 9, tutor # 1 maintained that when the topic of teaching materials being discussed was relatively heavy, more advanced and specialized English vocabulary was required. As a result, he motivated himself to enrich his English vocabulary before teaching his tutees. This aims at anticipating his tutees who may ask about the meaning of unusual English vocabulary [19]. Conversely, he did not specify what English

vocabulary was questioned by tutees. Based on this evidence, to support tutees in attaining more advanced and sophisticated English vocabulary, tutor # 1 introduced various synonyms, such as famous (known or well-known), temporize (delay), and procrastinate (postpone) to add their English vocabulary size [21].

3.2.3. Selecting appropriate and updated issues of English language teaching materials

Another solution is selecting the appropriate and updated issues of English teaching materials. To illustrate, initially, tutor # 1 encountered a classic teaching challenge while teaching English speaking, namely students' learning disengagement. This disengagement was represented in the students' English-speaking practices. They seemed uninterested in the presented teaching materials. This was manifested by their irresponsible attitudes toward their tutees. Also, it could be viewed from their facial expressions as signifying learning boredom. To tackle this learning disengagement, tutor # 1 claimed that employing the most current and relevant teaching materials (topics) presumably help tutees engage in English-speaking practices. Further, he also perceived that updating teaching materials of speaking added more knowledge and references. Equally important, it enabled him to explore deeper what he knew, what he wanted to know, and what he had learned.

Excerpt 12: "Hmm, the special guide doesn't seem to be just in this institution, sometimes giving instructions or giving examples of sentences, sometimes it's hoped that it can be a bit funny, easy to understand and the topic is also more millennial or up to date ... make examples that are more relevant to them ... so it's fitting to deliver the material better (Interview transcript of Tutor # 2 June 9th, 2023)."

Dealing excerpt 12, tutor # 2 contended that providing clear directions, simple examples (e.g. sentences or utterances), and enjoyable and updated topics allows him to facilitate tutees in understanding the basic concepts of delivered teaching materials [16]. Moreover, such activities encouraged them to practice those learned teaching materials [15]. Also, he noted that giving relevant and appropriate teaching materials with practical examples enabled tutees to understand and practice each concept in teaching materials, particularly for speaking skills.

3.2.4. Motivating English language tutees

The last solution to resolve the challenges during teaching English speaking in *Kampung Inggris* is motivating English language tutees. Tutor # 2 stipulated that motivating tutees to learn more actively and interactively is the most predominant key to reaching successful learning outcomes. He motivated his tutees to be confident in communicating their ideas orally in English. Even, he convinced his tutees that making mistakes and being confused during English-speaking activities were common (natural) since they were in the process of learning ("Wrong and confusion are natural because it is the process of learning").

Excerpt 13: "In the end, giving motivations like that ... rich still enthusiastic to learn huh! Wrong and confusion are natural because it is the process of learning. Different people, yes, there should be different ways to motivate him to encourage there are those who are easy, and some are difficult (Interview transcript of tutor # 2, June 7th, 2023)."

Besides, he delineated that employing proper motivating strategies for diverse tutees remains vital since each tutees possessed miscellaneous language learning strategies and characteristics. Given these facts, teaching challenges and possible solutions revealed from the tutors' experiences are expected to shed light on other English practitioners for attaining learning outcomes effectively [22], [23]. In addition, the study's pedagogical consequences include information on the need for fluency-based learning activities in addition to accuracy-based ones in English language instruction programs [24] and to obtain a more representative scope of inquiry, it is recommended that future research investigate teacher professional development (TPD) [25] while instructing English speaking in *Kampung Inggris*.

4. CONCLUSION

The study attempts to scrutinize the challenges and solutions of tutors during teaching English speaking in *Kampung Inggris*. On the one hand, the findings outline those tutors encountered several teaching challenges in English speaking, namely tutor's inability of exploring English language teaching materials, tutors' insufficient English vocabulary, tutors' ineffective time management during language teaching practices, demotivated tutees to learn English, and perceived teaching anxiety. On the other hand, tutors also performed a number of solutions to cope with those challenges, namely building a good rapport between tutor and tutees, tutor's self-motivation to English vocabulary enrichment, selecting appropriate and

updated issues of English language teaching materials, and motivating English language tutees. By understanding the challenges and solutions of teaching English speaking in *Kampung Inggris*, the conceptualisation, implementation, and evaluation of teaching English speaking can be managed more effectively. Equally important, empowering students to have a strong willingness to communicate in English is an inevitable issue that should be taken into account, notably in the EFL context.

The pedagogical implications of this study are to provide information that foreign language learning practices (English) should not only emphasize on accuracy-based learning activities but also fluency-based activities. This paradigmatic shift enables both teachers and students to use English as a communicative tool in which meaning making is the primary goal of English language learning rather than memorizing vocabulary and analyzing grammatical constituents. With this in mind, teaching and learning English in countries where English is officially spoken as a second and foreign language. Hence, TESOL practitioners, language learners and linguists may consider the vital roles of form, function and meaning of a language in the real communication contexts.

Although this study offers valuable contributions to the empirical issue of teaching English speaking in Indonesia, particularly in a language immersion program, such as *Kampung Inggris*, it unveils some limitations. The present study simply focused on the tutors' challenges and solutions during teaching English speaking in *Kampung Inggris*. Further studies are suggested to explore TPD during teaching English speaking in *Kampung Inggris* to gain a more representative scope of inquiry. In addition, the current study merely employed a single data collection technique (semi-structured interviews), future inquiries should involve multiple data collection techniques to triangulate data collection techniques, such as document analysis and observations to obtain more credible, and dependable collected data.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We express our deep gratitude to the Institute for Research and Community Services (*LPPM*) Universitas Siliwangi for providing financial and professional supports to conduct and develop this investigative project.

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